

Where did all the gold go?

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...and the answer is: NOONE SHOULD CARE!

What follows is an attempt to reconstruct the economic policy of the United States of America approximately since the founding of the Federal Reserve System in late 1913. Essentially the question since that time until this very day has been, unknowingly to all, where (and who) has all the gold? In my view, Keynes, Friedman, Mises, Hayek all knew the underlying issue of gold leakage from public ownership into private (anarchist-banker) hands, and published various theories explaining the 'effects' of this privation of gold to essentially keep the system going. However, I am getting a little head of myself, let us jump right in to my personal estimation of historic Federal Reserve System policy.

So, it's 1913 and the Federal Reserve System (hereafter just 'the Fed') pops into existence – what is its first priority? Buy gold, and as much of it as possible. This is because of the looming war in Europe, and the very rapid and real possibility of the involvement of the United States of America in that war. At the same time, the Fed must be willing to supply (backstop) 'money' in order to buy up any war-bonds issued by the United States Treasury. In turn the United States Treasury has the power to 'mint its way out' of any crisis but doesn't for a very simple reason: it is highly inflationary in a symbolic sense, as the coins it mints are always (implicitly) made 'of gold' and sticking a large denomination – so in the modern example of 1 Trillion dollar - valuation on a coin – even once – effectively re-values gold to that value in dollars, per ounce. So, at the time when the United States of America was but one of many competing global powers – particularly seemingly inferior to the British Empire in terms of Naval Supremacy (and resulting privateering 'rights') – the workaround of the Federal Reserve System is born – the Fed buys gold using issued dollar bills, and also buys United States treasury bonds with issued dollar bills, and this is ultimately backed up by the 'feasibility' of the United States of America Treasury 're-capitalizing' the Fed with an arbitrary denomination (gold) coin if things somehow 'went too far' – basically only realistically in the case of the United States of America losing a Naval war or during an ongoing civil war (or both).

So, the Fed buys gold and simultaneously buys United States of America Treasury bonds, and all seems good, except there is a problem: private (anarchist-banker) actors see this is going on, and want to start their own systems – without having to support a state and particularly a Navy, of course. What these private anarchist-banker actors do is buy their own gold, and

use the gold as a nucleus (to use a particle physics term) to form companies; the gold is the ultimate security when approaching one of (several) private banks to take out loans. Now banks are aware of this and typically ask for the gold to be stored in their own vaults – so what the private anarchist bankers do – is instead (try to and sometimes succeed) get their gold stored with a large commercial trust (it would I believe be called a unit trust today) who in turn keep the gold in... the Federal Reserve System vaults themselves. With the gold ‘safely in the Federal Reserve System’ (or other very large monitored commercial trust vault), banks are willing to lend against the gold in a secure holding not in their own hands – not knowing of course that these anarchist-banker actors are repeating the same trick across multiple banks.

Now with multiple loans in hand against the same gold – effectively using highly regulated (by the Fed) banks to form a large pool of (regulated bank) capital (so roughly speaking gold-backed-M1), after using a fraction to buy back the original gold (on the ‘open market’ operations of the Fed or effectively so through large commercial wholesalers) so as the private anarchist-banker actor now has the original gold in hand – which they will typically bury like many tree faring rodents are wont to do – please be clear when I say this, these anarchist-bankers are NOT Jews these are the people THAT BLAME their actions on Jews – they now have a large amount of (gold-backed-M1) and use it to found a ‘real’ company, often a (small) bank or a (small) bank servicing company or a bank consultancy. What that small company will do will then spend the money on ‘looking good’ services – so an anti-money laundering company ‘founded’ by a big 4 consultancy firm for example – in order to suck in more funding from the regulated (gold-backed-M1) banks, while the money in turn is used to fund the ‘real’ companies owned by the anarchist-bankers – consultancy firms. These ‘small’ projects then fail and the stock price of these larger consultancy firms is inflated – however the trick does not stop there. The stock price of these larger consultancy firms (so then as now, from marketing to sales, to operations to implementation to staffing) is then inflated, and the stocks themselves start to become ‘money’ – as in the stocks in turn can be ‘tradable for good and/or services’. The underlying anarchist-banker actors are aware of this and use their ultimate beneficial ownership of the stocks to leverage more loans – through the same trick as with the original gold. The stocks themselves (under their own names) are placed in a central holding unit trust (Vanguard is a modern example) and those anarchist-banker actors can then use that ‘centrally held and validated’ stock as a basis to secure multiple loans from different regulated (gold-M1-backed – even today they are gold backed through the Fed as will be explained below) large commercial banks. Again, they then use this large pool of private regulated bank money to repurchase the original stock (on the ‘open market’ through investment banks), maybe some gold on the side, and then use the large amount of money to either repeat the same trick with stocks (back in 1913 onwards) or today buy crypto through Tether ‘pseudo’ (crypto) dollars (‘stable-coins’). Tether in turn cannot pass an audit because of the NAMES on the treasury bonds they hold in

security against their – one FEC tweet with ‘T○’ and nothing else would collapse the entire crypto market overnight and everyone knows this or should know it of course.

Okay, that is jumping ahead over the entire system, let’s go back to 1913 and see what happens. The Fed knows that it has to buy gold and buy treasury bonds and somehow keep inflation – the daily cost of goods and services is the only number the Fed can really look at or control from its point of view as it knows asset prices MUST explode in this system it has no overall control over - from increasing rapidly. It does this by setting an interest rate policy that essentially compresses the regulated bank (gold-backed-M1 and M2 but the ‘same’ almost in this context – so ‘regulated’ money) money supply. So, an increase in short (overnight) or long (treasury) interest rates amount to the same thing – changes in (different kinds of but still regulated) overall money supply. However, the problem with this system is again anarchist-banker actors who want ‘in’ on the money printing game without any of the hassle of supporting a state, handling taxes and above all funding a Navy (and eventually an Air Force, Marine Corps, Army, and generally speaking ‘foundational, safe for a republic to form’ statecraft). What these anarchist bankers do is step in not with ‘regulated money’ – but with stocks, simply with stocks, which become tradable for goods and services ‘as if they are money’. So, from 1913 all the way through to (actually even until today as will be explained below but for now let us say) 1929, the Fed is buying gold (through certificates or simply buying proxies such as mortgage backed securities secures on houses owned by large conglomerates owned by anarchist bankers who secure everything through gold and that is where the money goes when the Fed buys MBS – again jumping by a century but it is always the same playbook) and buying United States of America Treasuries and controlling the system ‘somehow’ with interest rates that just collapse gold-backed-M1 and lead to more use of ‘stocks as money’ (Vanguard pension system, basically).

Right so what happens in 1929 that changes everything? The Fed runs out of gold. So, the anarchists-banker actors get so greedy (they know this will happen and plan for it) that they have all their loans listed in their names (or a fake name derived for this purpose), and roughly agree on a date to throw straw filled dummies out of the window of high-rise Manhattan office blocks to make it ‘look like’ they didn’t see it coming. Underneath it all they have run off with the gold in private underground bunkers or otherwise secured under alternate aliases. Then comes the great depression – what is happening – actually it is the same thing, nothing has changed at all. The main difference is that stock prices have collapsed, and so ‘pseudo’ money has disappeared altogether (an analogy for what will happen when the crypto-bubble eventually bursts) – and so it ‘looks like’ the money supply has collapsed – and so the Fed tries to increase the money supply – but can’t – as it has run out of gold. This situation actually continues from then on – the Fed never again gets hold of

gold, and is constantly on the hunt for gold proxies (eventually leading to Mortgage Backed Securities and now a Cryptocurrency strategic reserve).

In this framework, World War 2 was a 'hunt for gold', and eventually ends in an armistice as no one can find it. Events like the Nixon shock 'de-pegging' from gold, symbolically ending the Bretton Woods framework, then are planned events – everyone knew the gold was gone, and it was planned to have a period of high interest rates afterwards to ensure that financial stability (consumer prices) could return to a relatively stable rate up until the (end of) the Volcker shock. All that continued until relatively speaking 'today', when events like the 2022 high inflation from COVID19 spending/stimulus; the inability to remove Russia from the financial system in 2022; the inability to let even small banks like Silicon Valley Bank in 2022 go without immediately adding additional cushioning 'to the system' using the Bank Term Funding Program; the inability of the Fed to let the UK 'fend for itself' on the Liability Driven Investments pensions crisis also in 2022. This is before adding that many countries (seemingly) hostile to USA intentions such as China can create 'at-will' dollar swap lines using their large volume of treasury holdings and the effective necessity of the Fed to buy such treasury holdings to maintain financial stability.

And so, all things seem dire, until...duh duh duh!

The US Treasury mints a single 1 dollar wooden coin made of slave ship wood (with Obama's head on the reverse – reverse to symbolise the end of slavery) and deposits it in the treasury general account at the Federal Reserve. This symbolic action immediately shows the US Treasury taking control of its finances – secure in the knowledge that the US Navy (and air-force in principle) is unassailable and so if the US Treasury declares that 'wood is money now' then the rest of the world simply has to accept it due to the US Navy's implied privateering rights. At the same time other countries could also move away from US Treasuries (and implicitly gold) as backing their currencies; I suggest using depleted uranium as an easily state-hoard-able metal of considerable use, and if it is ever stolen, can be traced relatively easily with Geiger counters. Starting with the wooden coin, this combined set of actions should see treasury yields (at all durations) head to zero, and all assets go through the roof, with mildly deflationary consumer goods effects and highly positive labour value effects. At the same time, the Fed (and corresponding central banks in other countries) should then be able to effectively target the outliers / fraudsters as they will have had the 'largest increase in apparent asset valuation'. Lastly it is worth noting that one asset does plunge in value on this decision – gold (and silver and perhaps platinum to some degree) – as it becomes effectively worthless as 'difficult to obtain slightly better conductor than copper' and not much else.

Per guidelines, this work is published under my 'passport name' (deadname). My real name is Lucy Mavek Trump; we all get to choose our own names after transitioning, and this is mine.

This work is dedicated to those truly perfect beings, Belle-Delphine